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Exploring the scientific discourse: the new perspectives about energy geopolitics

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Introduction

Energy is a decisive factor for the economic development in modern societies (Armeanu, Joldes, Gherghina, & Andrei, 2021; Bayar & Gavriletea, 2019; Muhammad, 2019; Oatley, 2021; Omri, 2014; Palle, 2021). According to the US Energy Information Administration (EIA), demand is expected to rise by 50% by 2050, owing primarily to non-OECD economic growth and population growth, particularly in Asia (Nalley & LaRose, 2021). Nowadays, fossil fuels meet 80% of global energy demand (REN21, 2021) and accounts for 73% of human-caused greenhouse gas emissions (Lamb et al., 2021). To avoid an increase in the frequency and severity of dangerous and unprecedented weather extremes, such as heatwaves, devastating floods, population displacement, and loss of lives and livelihoods, global CO² emissions must be cut in half by 2030.

Despite of Europe is already in the grip of an energy crisis, Russian military action in Ukraine could worsen the situation, not only because President Putin could cut off natural gas exports, but also because of the ability to disrupt global oil markets, which would directly affect US consumers. The global supply/demand equation related to oil is very tight even with Russia's millions of barrels per day coming onto the market. For all these reasons, energy plays a major role in geopolitics. Indeed, there has been a surge of interest around energy in recent decades, prompting a slew of other reviews and analyses. Nevertheless, while some narratives have covered key areas such as energy policy (Jenkins, McCauley, Heffron, Stephan, & Rehner, 2016), energy resources (Evans, Strezov, & Evans, 2012), and sustainable development (Dincer & Acar, 2015), to the best of our knowledge, no contributions have covered the field of energy geopolitics.

The confrontation of discourses over energy during the last decades diversified. The scientific field was one of the most significant and dynamic. The study of some national or regional cases contribute to understanding better this relation between scientific, public sphere/media and political discourse. The Russian case is particularly interesting in this dialogue because the political power announces a clear reception of the scientific discourse about the human-generated climate change and the need for a new energy paradigm in the Medvedev presidency, moving to a very different discourse after 2012, under Putin presidency, who turned the energy into a national issue (Tynkkynen & Tynkkynen, 2018). The study of the US situation is also

significant, where there is the confrontation between negationists of climate change and the defenders of the human-generated climate change in political and scientific discourses. Finally, in the EU case, the debate over energy supply diversification (Hofmann & Staeger, 2018) and the full reception of the principle of the human-generated climate crisis, driving to a direct intervention in the way energy was produced and distributed, penetrated political discourse. Accordingly, with this trend, many national parliaments became the floor for debate about public policies and confrontation over different energy development conceptions, inclusively responding to civil society demands for a further discussion about "energy democracy" (Williams & Sovacool, 2020).

For to the determinant role of energy in human development and how humans relate to the environment, managing energy resources and transportation became one of the most significant concerns of political powers (Urbina, 2022). Consequently, any change in the energy production and use paradigm will result in readjustments of the international order and open new geopolitical perspectives on the place and role each state plays in international politics. In the last decades, the direct connection between sustainable growth, development, and energy became evident (Ali, Raza, Narjis, Saeed, & Khan, 2020; Silva, Távora, & Mendonça, 2022). Accordingly, political agenda-setting based on energy concern emerged.

This research aims to answer two broad questions: has scientific discourse about energy geopolitics shifted where is produced or the topics being discussed? Is scientific discourse changing in response to changes in political discourse on energy and energy geopolitics? We extract the past two decades of scientific discourse from the Scopus database, combining the analysis of scientific discourse itself with bibliometric data. This work addresses these questions in two folds: the identity of scientific discourse producers and the analysis of scientific discourse itself.

Evolution in energy geopolitics thinking

Bibliometric materials proved to be very useful in the analysis of emerging trends related to contemporary societal challenges such as radical wireless technologies (e.g. Mendonça et al., 2022), governance concepts like the "circular economy" (e.g. de Jesus, Antunes, Santos, & Mendonça, 2018), innovation studies (Santos & Mendonça, 2022), Sustainability-oriented service innovation (Calabrese, Castaldi, Forte, & Levialdi, 2018), African research (Confraria & Godinho, 2015) and National Systems of Innovation (Teixeira, 2014). In this work, we will bring insights from the quantitative studies of science to the understanding the global debates regarding energy geopolitics.

For this purpose, we collect the scientific discourse from the Scopus database (Boyle & Sherman, 2008; Moed, Aisati, & Plume, 2011; Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016; Thelwall & Sud, 2022). Scopus is the world's largest database of peer-reviewed literature, with over 82 million document and more than 1.7 billion cited references ("Why choose Scopus - Scopus benefits | Elsevier solutions," 2021). It includes journals from the Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities, as well as Science, Technology, and Medicine.

All references containing the terms "geopolitics" and "energy" in the title, keyword, or abstract until the year of 2021 were selected and extracted. In addition, articles' titles, authors name,

journals titles, years of publication and affiliation addresses were retrieved. This search identified 1653 different documents, encompassing 1566 research articles, 86 conference papers and 1 conference review. Books, book chapters, editorial, erratum, letter note, retracted, review, and short survey documents were excluded. Figure 1 shows the increasing trend in the number of articles published per year with these conditions.

Figure 1. Number of papers published in journals and conferences per year with the expression "geopolitics" and "energy".

A preliminary examination of the data revealed that not all journals are equally interested in these terms, and that their interest varies over time. From the 680 different source titles which published the 1653 manuscripts, 440 only published one manuscript and 121 issued two in this forty years period. Figure 2 depicts the number of articles published per journal over a 20-year period to demonstrate how the number of articles published has changed over time. Only journals with at least five articles published between 2002 and 2021 were considered, in a total of 57 journals.

Figure 2. Distribution of the number of articles published by each journal through the years.

There were clearly more journals publishing articles after 2012. Figure 2 depicts 42 journals from 2002 to 2011 and 55 source titles from 2012 to 2021 suggesting a rising interest in these topics. To understand the geographic distribution of the authors of these 1653 manuscripts, the affiliation was considered.

Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the frequency of authors affiliated with each country over the two time periods: in orange between 2002 and 2011, and blue between 2012 and 2021. The darker the colours, higher the frequency of authors affiliated with local institutions in the country.

Figure 3. Frequency of authors affiliated per country (2002-2011).

Figure 4. Frequency of authors affiliated per country (2012-2021).

It is clear that the countries hosting the highest number of authors until 2011 were US and UK. From 2012 on, the United Kingdom increases even more the number authors in these field and countries like China, India and Russia emerged hosting a large number of authors. These new countries are mainly from the Southern Hemisphere and East.

The new players and the most important channels

Besides the growing number of scientific publications in the field, some journals continue to publish and contribute new knowledge to the subject. Figure 5 shows the number of manuscripts containing these expressions published in the top thirteen source titles over two ten-year periods (2002-2011 vs 2012-2021).

Figure 5. Frequency of articles published by the journals top 13 in the time periods between 2002 and 2011 and between 2012 and 2021.

Only five of the 13 identified journals were found to be common to both time periods: *Geopolitics*, *Energy Policy*, *Political Geography*, *Eurasian Geography and Economics* and

Geopolitics of Energy. With exception of *Geopolitics of Energy*, they also increase the number of articles published in the last decade with both expressions of interest reinforcing the importance of the topics. *Geopolitics of Energy* is the only one that decreased the number of articles published since 2011, indicating a drop in the interest. In the second decade, five journals began publishing manuscripts containing the words of interest in 2013, with two following suit in 2014. They were all among the top thirteen most prolific publishers.

The number of institutions that house researchers with similar interests has grown in tandem with the number of authors who publish in these fields. Considering only the 5 journals common to both decades, as identified in Figure 5, the institutions hosting authors responsible for at least two publications are depicted in

Figure 6 and

Figure 7, respectively, for the periods 2002 to 2011 and 2012 to 2021.

Figure 6. Institutions connected to the manuscripts published between 2002 and 2011.

Figure 7. Institutions connected to the manuscripts published between 2012 and 2021.

Based on the comparison between

Figure 6 *and*

Figure 7, it is possible to see not only the number of institutions publishing in this field raising but also producing more works in collaboration.

Figure 6 shows 25 different institutions that hosted authors who published at least two publications between 2001 and 2020, while

Figure 7 illustrates the increased number of institutions for 33 institutions. Besides, the only five institutions found to be common between both periods of time: Chinese Academy of Sciences, the University of British Columbia, the University College London, the University of Colorado, and the University of Oxford. Last two ones also revealed to have increased their stock of publications in the field for the second period. This trend of increasing the research round those topics was also noticed for other journals as in the first decade, only seven institutions had more than two publications (actually 3). The decade that followed revealed 9 institutions with more than two publications: six with three, two with four manuscripts, and one with five. The number of publications at the last three institutions increased from two in the first decade.

In addition, after 2012, the number of publications developed in collaboration also increased from four to six. The first period, the four publications detected were co-written by authors from the same country such as one from Louisiana State University and University of Wisconsin, other from University of Colorado and University of Oregon or even from the same city such as the pair of publications from Oxford Institute for Energy Studies and University of Oxford. In the following decade, international collaborations appear and publications co-authored by research from different countries became available such as the one shared by Cornell University, University of Colorado and University of Oslo.

The narrative developments over the time

Over the last two decades, various topics have piqued the interest of researchers and authors, and they have been addressed in manuscripts that have been published. Figure 8 shows the evolution of 16 expressions that we discovered had the greatest changes in frequency of usage.

Figure 8. Evolution of frequency of some expressions of interested used over the 20 years period.

Although some expressions, such as "crude oil," "energy policy," and "energy supply," showed a slight increase, others showed a simultaneous increase. For example, in some years, the terms "natural gas," "renewable energy," and "energy security" were used more than 50 times. The EU's political discourse reflects this concern about "climate change" and "energy security." The issue of security became increasingly linked to the diversification of energy suppliers (Strigunov, Manoilo, Rozhin, & Simons, 2022). The reliance on a single supplier has been identified as one of the major vulnerabilities of EU energy policy (Tichý, 2020).

Although intriguing, the rising trend and many instances of "geopolitical risk" in 2020 and 2021 can be somehow justified by the evolution of the energy market and the rearrangements for supply and transportation. Along with these developments, many other concepts related to the central ones, such as "energy" and "geopolitics," were added over time. For instance, in the MENA, US power diminished, and, simultaneously, other powers entered the equation (e.g. Russia, Cina, Iran and Turkey). The Arab Spring brought more substantial involvement of some of these powers, like the Russian Federation's case (Strigunov et al., 2022). As for China, the international project Belt & Road also brought a new discourse for energy issues and a replacement of this discourse in the international sphere (Costa, 2020). Therefore, the rise of "clean energy" seen as the future and as the way for sustainable growth and development did not end the concern with fossil and not clean energies, such as oil and gas. Part of the disagreements and geopolitical alignments over energy is still about the supply and transportation of not clean energies. As some authors refer to, multipolarity is increasing in many regional areas; political power disputes result from this situation (Strigunov et al., 2022). To understand the occurrence of words and their relationships, Figure 9 was created to show the discourse relations during the first decade.

Figure 9. Network of co-occurring words in the abstracts published between 2002 and 2011.

During this period, some words such as “energy”, “security”, “politics”, “governance”, “Russia”, “Europe”, “oil” and “gas” became increasingly intertwined, demonstrating the rise of energy production, commercialization, and transportation as one of the most pressing issues in a so-called transition period from carbon-intensive energy to clean energy. Some of them were the clusters' focal points a decade ago. Two words, however, remain at the heart of clusters: “oil” and “geopolitic”. They were both inundated with new ideas. In addition to “oil”, “price” appears frequently, as it is a current concern for European countries. Concepts such as “visions”, “implications” and “regionalism” are also discussed in relation to “geopolitics”. As new clusters, one may be associated with “crisis” and “Ukraine”, one with “nuclear” and “power”, and one with “change” and other concepts such as “climate” and “terror”, which result from particular attention to the competition for energy and also to the disruptive situations resulting from this competition.

Conclusion

Since at least the year 2000, there has been an exponential increase in the number of publications in the field of energy geopolitics. Between 2002 and 2021, 57 journals were found to have published at least five manuscripts, increasing from 42 between 2001 and 2010 to 52 between 2011 and 2020. The geographical distribution of the producers also increased in the second decade, with an increase in the number of authors in the United Kingdom, China, and other Southern Hemisphere and East European countries. These findings point to a geographical multipolarization of scientific discourse which we addressed in this work.

In both decades, the data collected revealed five institutions that stood out for producing manuscripts during both time periods, as well as 20 newcomers to the list of leading producers of scientific discourse. International collaboration to produce scientific discourse also emerged along with the increased number of manuscripts published.

The discourse on energy geopolitics has also evolved to express widespread concern about geopolitical risk. As the main topics evolved over time, many other ideas and concepts were added. For example, the terms "Ukraine" and "crisis," as well as "nuclear" and "power," have become frequently used, reflecting recent political concerns and discourse. The field's evolution will continue in the coming years, and it will be critical to monitor the concepts that gain traction.

Nonetheless, by taking stock in this way, the study has several implications for the field. It sheds light over two decades of research output as well as a concise summary of key trends. It may also provide a solid foundation for interested scholars to broaden their collaboration networks to include a more diverse group of collaborators, potentially increasing the relevance of analyses. Finally, the study's findings can help new researchers gain a better understanding of global trends and critical institutions.

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